

Journal home page:
<http://www.iajpr.com/index.php/en/>

INDO AMERICAN
JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL
RESEARCH

Review Article: Carbon Nanotubes Treats Cancer

A Arun kumar*¹, Subal debnath¹, Arghya Acharjee², Saurav Nandi²,

¹Sr ikrupa Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vil. Velkatta, Kondapak (mdl), Dist. Medak, Siddipet, Andhra Pradesh – 502 277.

²Aurobindo Pharma Ltd, Maitrivihar, Ameerpet, Hyderabad, A.P.

ARTICLE INFO

Received 17 March 2011
Received in revised form 21
April 2011
Accepted 25 September 2011
Available online October 2011

Keywords

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs),
Functionalisation of CNTs,
Targeting by CNTs,
Toxicity of CNTs and IN-
Vivo research news.

ABSTRACT

This article examines an over view about Carbon nanotubes, their properties which are useful to treat cancer barriers for implementing targeted delivery of cancer treatment drugs by using carbon nanotubes (CNTs). It was established that this technology is highly viable as a means of treating cancer but its development was still immature. The group found a number of key areas that could potentially be explored further in research, but ultimately recommend the further exploration of issues surrounding toxicity of CNTs in medical applications. Carbon nanotubes can be used in various therapeutic applications like cancer therapy, intracellular targeting, prolonged systemic circulation, vaccine adjuvant, per oral absorption, ocular delivery, DNA delivery, oligonucleotide delivery applications. The main advantage of using CNTs as a drug carrier compared to free drug is the potential to target delivery for selective destruction of certain types of cells, reducing the toxicity to non-targeted cells. As the micro-environments of extra cellular tissues of tumors and intracellular lysosomes and endosomes are acidic, the situation will potentially facilitate the active drug release from SW-CNT delivery vehicles. Hence CNTs shows potential for selective and specific targeting of cells. Recently, there have been new studies on carbon nanotubes which have given cancer patients and their loved ones new hope to beat this terrible disease. This type of research could be the future of fighting cancer or other diseases and it is going to be up to chemical engineers and people in related fields to continue this research to better the world. For our paper we intend to elaborate on the discussion of this existing technology and to tell how it is being developed into a better cancer fighter.

Corresponding author

A .Arun kumar,

Email: subal_2007@yahoo.co.in

Sri krupa Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vil: Velkatta, Mdl: Kondapak,
Dist: Medak, Siddipet Andhra Pradesh – 502277. Phone: 09666690052.

Please cite this article in press as A .Arun kumar et al., Carbon Nanotubes Treats Cancer. Indo American Journal of Pharm Research.2011;1(5):264-276.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a malignant disease which spreads to distant parts of the body and as a result is incurable. Current treatment methods are crude and most result in the damage of healthy tissue since the medicine is indiscriminate. CNTs can be used for targeted delivery of anti-cancer agents even though small fibrous materials such as carbon, glass or asbestos are a known environmental cancer risk. The group has been hypothetically approached by a wealthy philanthropist who is looking to donate money to this sector and needs to know the current state of the field. Specifically the research group has decided to focus on CNTs as the method of cancer treatment. In this scenario money is no object so even the most expensive treatments have been considered [1].

Comparison of Nanomedicine to Conventional Treatment of Cancer

Current treatment such as surgery is hindered by accessibility to tumorous cells and the risk of operation near or on vital organs. Also selective treatment in chemotherapy and radiation is limited. On the whole, present treatment methods are not very effective at stopping the spread or recurrence of cancer. Nanomedicine provides a means of targeted delivery of drugs. Since the cancerous cells are on the nanoscale, there is a potential for highly efficient drug delivery has two major benefits. First, the total quantity of drug required is less, a concern primarily associated with the more costly drugs.

Additionally no solvent is required for delivery of the drug, which means that unwanted health effects from the solvent can be prevented. Second, a lower concentration of the toxin is delivered to other parts of the body, without the risk of the protective nanocarrier degrading. Thus, fewer health side effects are suffered by the patient undergoing treatment. A further advantage of nanocarriers is that a range of drugs can be attached for a variety of purposes including; therapeutic, diagnostic, targeting and barrier avoiding effectively allowing a toolkit to enable treatment specific to each patient's cancer.

Properties of Carbon Nanotubes

One of the most notable characteristics of the material is a high tensile strength. This has led to serious consideration of the possibility of reaching outer space elevators are far-fetched but the successful use of CNTs in medicine has already been proven in the laboratory. A multitude of medical applications have been found. In this field there are three main attributes of CNTs which have been exploited

- Their small size.
- Their high surface area to volume ratio.
- Their ability to contain chemicals

Carbon nanotubes can be produced small enough to pass through holes in tumours or to transport DNA [1]. The large surface to volume ratio provides a good platform for efficient transportation of chemicals and the reactions needed for ultra-sensitive glucose detection [2]. The content of this article has been mostly directed at the third point a technique specific to only a few nanotechnologies including CNTs - which is to transport encapsulated toxins which can be released at a diseased site. Carbon nanotubes can be produced small enough to pass through holes in tumours or to transport DNA.

DRUG DELIVERY BY CARBON NANOTUBES^[2]

If it possible to target the delivery of chemotherapeutic agents to only the tumour cells then this would decrease both the adverse side effects and also allow more effective, concentrated doses/agents that would be too toxic for traditional chemotherapy. Systems being used currently for drug delivery include dendrimers, polymers, and liposomes, but carbon nanotubes present the opportunity to work with effective structures that have high drug loading capacities and good cell penetration qualities.

These nanotubes function with a larger inner volume to be used as the drug container, large aspect ratios for numerous functionalization attachments, and the ability to be readily taken up by the cell. Because of their tube structure, carbon

nanotubes can be made with or without end caps, meaning that without end caps the inside where the drug is held would be more accessible. Right now with carbon nanotube drug delivery systems, problems arise like the lack of solubility, clumping occurrences, and half-life. The advantages of carbon nanotubes as nanovectors for drug delivery remain where cell uptake of these structures was demonstrated efficiently where the effects were prominent, showing the particular nanotubes can be less harmful as

nanovehicles for drugs(see in fig 1). Also, drug encapsulation has been shown to enhance water dispersibility, better bioavailability, and reduced toxicity. All of these result in a good drug delivery basis where further research and understanding could improve upon numerous other advancements, like increased water solubility, decreased toxicity, sustained half-life, increased cell penetration and uptake, all of which are currently novel but undeveloped ideas.

Figure 1: Showing the technique behind passive targeting. A localized defect in endothelial spacing allows nanoparticles to permeate into the tumour body where they will accumulate readily and leads to cell death.

DRUG LOADING

Opening, Filling and Capping of Carbon Nanotubes^{[3], [4]}

A selection of filling and capping techniques has been used for CNTs. The appropriate method depends on the material that is to be inserted into the CNT. The criteria include the melting temperature, reactivity, surface tension and sensitivity of the material. Carbon nanotubes can

either be filled during synthesis or afterwards. Adding the contents of the nanotubes in-situ tends to be a less efficient approach producing a yield of around 10% whereas the post synthesis process can be better controlled and yields of 50-100% are achievable. An example of the spontaneously produced “peapod” formation of a CNT filled with KI atoms can be seen in Figure: 2

Figure 2: Scanning electron micrograph of a KI filled CNT.

Post synthesis production of CNTs implies that is necessary to open the ends This can be accomplished by passing electric currents through the CNT, attacking the CNT with acid which corrodes the angled parts of the tube the most (i.e. the ends) or oxidization using carbon dioxide [3].

There are two ways to include foreign particles in CNTs. One category is decoration which is the process of bonding a functional group to CNTs. This is difficult as carbon is rather inert, so oxidisation is used to produce a more reactive attachment surface. The functional group is either bonded to the inside or outside of the walls. The most common mechanism for filling CNTs is capillarity. The limiting factor in capillarity is the diameter of the CNT and the surface tension of the material [4] in aqueous solutions hydrophobic and Van der Waals forces also play a role.

For chemicals with higher surface tensions it is possible to lower this tension by creating a suitable composite, which can be chemically reduced to the original substance once the CNT has been filled. The CNTs are washed using a solution which has been chosen to offer only limited solubility to the impregnating fluid and thus can dissolve only deposits left outside of the CNT. After filling, the CNTs are capped by passing a current which fuses the ends closed. The loading of CNTs is still an area requiring further research and more frequently mathematical methods are used rather than laboratory experiments due to the comparatively lower cost.

Attachment and Release to CNT

External attachment of drugs is usually achieved by attaching molecules by amide, ester or disulphide bonds. This is in order to employ a bond that is biologically cleaved either near the cell or more usefully, in the cell, releasing the payload. In a recent study, it was found that the lack of enhanced efficacy between the delivery of methotrexate, an anti cancer drug, and the nonconjugated drug was from the amide bond, attaching the drug to the f-CNT.

It was found this was too stable and was not biologically cleaved. Improved delivery can result from a bond that is biologically stable so as not to breakdown before it has reached the required location, but to be enzymatically cleaved within the cell. The use of NIR to release CNT encapsulated drugs is another promising release mechanism as living organisms are generally transparent to NIR. This is particularly applicable to polar drugs which do not readily cross the lipid bilayer. The NIR heats the CNT and can be used to accelerate the diffusion of the molecule inside the tube to the cell. Extremely low diffusion coefficients trap molecules of high polarity. When heated the diffusion coefficient increases up to 7 fold, facilitating the release of the polar drugs.

FUNCTIONALISATION of CNTs^[4]

CNTs have the potential to carry drugs in the organism as they are hollow and much smaller than the blood cells. The methods were developed for attaching DNA and protein molecules to the inside and outside of the nanotubes. This gives

one the ability to target and destroy individual cells that may be cancerous or infected by a virus. Significant progress in interfacing CNTs with biological materials has been made in key areas such as aqueous solubility, chemical and biological functionalization for biocompatibility and specificity, and in electronic sensing of proteins. In addition, the bio-conjugated nano-tubes combined with the sensitive nano-tube based electronic devices would enable sensitive bio-sensors toward medical diagnostics.

Functionalisation of CNTs is a process of chemical synthesis where desired functional groups can be introduced onto the walls of CNTs for various applications producing functionalised carbon nano tubes (f-CNT). Raw carbon nanotubes have highly hydrophobic surfaces and are not soluble in aqueous solutions and pristine CNTs are not soluble in any solution.

The aim of this process in cancer treatment is the enhancement of biocompatibility within the body, enhancement of encapsulation tendency and solubility, multimodal drug delivery and imaging with the specific properties imparted related to the desired function. Modifications to CNTs can be divided into two categories; covalent and non covalently bonded.

Covalent Bonding ^[5]

Covalent chemical bonding of polymer chains to CNTs results in strong chemical bonds between nanotubes and the attached molecule. Various covalent reactions have been developed to graft molecules based on their varying properties and can be further classified as Grafting to or Grafting from reactions which involve the addition of preformed polymer chains or the polymerisation of monomers from surface derived initiators on CNTs respectively.

Both to and from methods involve reaction to the surface of CNT by functionalisation reactions. Molecules or polymer chains reacting with the surface of pristine, pre-functionalised or oxidised CNTs are the three main methods used to attach molecules covalently.

Oxidation of CNTs, being one of the most common modifications, uses oxidising agents such as concentrated nitric acid to form carboxyl groups at the most reactive sites; i.e. the ends, which are more reactive, and on any defects on the walls, such as 5 membered rings [5].

The curvature of the CNT places a strain on the SP² hybridised carbon atoms, reducing the energy barrier required to convert the SP² hybridized bonds to SP³ compared with flat graphene. This results in pristine CNT being susceptible to various addition reactions.

Non-Covalent Bonding ^[6]

Non-covalent bonding of molecules to CNTs is generally the more widely used method of drug delivery according to literature. An ideal non-covalently functionalised CNT should have specific properties; the more closely matched, the greater the usefulness in biological roles.

This can be carried out by creating micelle type structures where amphiphilic molecules are coated to the CNT. Another common form of functionalisation is bonding achieved by stacking pyrene molecules onto the surface of the CNT. This type of bonding can also be applied to single strands of DNA by virtue of the aromatic DNA base units. This was shown to be unstable as it is cleaved by nucleases and so the biological applications are so far limited.

Figure 3: Covalent Bonding Functionalisation. a) Oxidation with nitric acid producing carboxyl functional groups, then conjugated with hydrophilic polymers b) Photo induced addition of azide compounds with CNT c) Bingel reaction on CNTs d) 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition on CNTs. R is a hydrophilic domain in biological applications or can be drugs/antibodies[5].

Non-covalent bonding does not disrupt the network. Except for a shortening of length the physical properties of the CNTs are essentially preserved, showing great promise for imaging and photothermal ablation [6].

CNTs must be nanosized to prevent cellular opsonisation (the susceptibility of the macromolecule to ingestion by phagocytes resulting in its destruction) by the innate immune system but also functionalised with molecules/polymer chains such as PEG which do not give an adaptive immune response. The CNT must also be of sufficient size to utilise the EPR effects and so a trade off is required. PEG is a useful in determining the optimal functionalisation degree as it is an easily controllable variable. This passive targeting can cause problems;

microspheres can lead to chemoembolism-type problems in the lymphatic nodes. For such cases, fictionalization with nanomagnetic particles (e.g. iron-oxide) and placing a magnet at the desired location for extended periods of time allows for drug release over an extended period.

Active targeting requires fictionalization with tumour specific binding sites to selectively bind to tumour cells. Many cells of various cancers are known to over express certain receptors, such as brain tumours showing typically 100k to 900k LDL (low density lipoprotein) receptors. Functionalizing CNTs with LDL not only increases uptake dramatically in the cancer cells, but reduces uptake in other cells with far fewer LDL receptors.

Figure 4: Non-covalent functionalisation. a) Pyrene molecules anchored on SWCNT surface via π - π stacking on the surface b) DNA attached via π - π stacking c) A CNT functionalised with PEGylated phospholipids [6].

TARGETTING OF CNTs

CNTs are being developed as targeted delivery vehicles for anticancer drugs right into cancer cells - think of really, really tiny injection needles. They are also used as the therapeutic agent itself; there is research that shows that CNTs can act as nanoscale bombs that literally blow apart a cancer cell. Particularly single-walled CNTs (SWCNTs) are under active development for various biomedical applications.

Coupling the CNT with biomolecules, such as proteins, is a good method for targeting specific

sites but has the disadvantage of either reducing protein activity or CNT absorption or both. A novel method demonstrates that it is possible to achieve complete retention of enzymatic activity of adsorbed proteins as well as retention of a substantial fraction of the near-infrared (NIR) absorption of SWCNTs.

Passive and Active Targeting

The first is passive (or size-mediated) targeting this relies upon the unique size of nanoparticles and the growth behaviour of tumours. As the tumour grows it requires greater and greater

amounts of oxygen and nutrients, engaging new blood vessels by a process called angiogenesis. Unlike in regular blood vessels the endothelial cells (which regulate the transfer of molecules across the vessel) in tumours can be spaced as far apart as 600nm from each other.

This defect allows increased permeability of nanoparticles into the interstitial space. In addition there is poor lymphatic drainage in these tumourous areas. These combined effects lead to phenomena known as enhanced permeability and retention (EPR). By proper design of nanoparticles this effect can be harnessed to locally increase density of nanoparticles (and their therapeutic agents) in the tumour, up to at least 10 times that of drugs not transported via nanoparticles.

Another effect of angiogenesis and the desire to increase supply of nutrients to the tumour cell is the process of glycolysis used to increase energy level. This has the resulting effect of a locally decreased pH. This could potentially be utilised as an effective means of controlled drug release within the cancerous tumour, given a nanotube capped with a substance biodegradable by an acidic environment (Misra et al., 2010)[2].

The second technique is active targeting - this involves using antibody- or ligand-targeted binding as a means of selective delivery to cancer cells or tumours. This technique requires knowledge of the target receptor or antigen on the cancer cells, preferably with a number of properties that are unique to the cancer cells and that are expressed with high enough density to distinguish them from surrounding healthy cells

Tumor targeting^[11]

Research has been conducted on in vivo biodistribution and highly efficient tumor targeting of carbon nanotubes in mice for cancer therapy. Investigations are being done on the biodistribution of radio-labelled SWNTs in mice by in vivo positron emission tomography (PET), ex vivo biodistribution and Raman spectroscopy.

It was found that SWNTs that are functionalized with phospholipids bearing polyethylene-glycol (PEG) are surprisingly stable in vivo.

The effect of PEG chain length on the biodistribution and circulation of the SWNTs was studied. Effectively PEGylated SWNTs exhibited relatively long blood circulation times and low uptake by the reticuloendothelial system (RES). Efficient targeting of integrin positive tumor in mice was achieved with SWNTs coated with PEG chains linked to an arginine-glycine-aspartic acid (RGD) peptide. A high tumor accumulation was attributed to the multivalent effect of the SWNTs.

The Raman signatures of SWNTs were used to directly probe the presence of nanotubes in mice tissues and confirm the radio-label-based results.

Factors Affecting CNTs's Toxicity^{[7], [8]}

The following is a list of factors that have been shown to influence the degree of toxicity of CNTs (Ji et al., 2010);

- Concentration of dose
- SWCNTs vs. MWCNTs
- Length
- Catalyst residue
- Degree of aggregation
- Oxidisation
- Functionalisation.

Whilst many studies show conflicting results on some of these properties, two seem to yield the most con-current results; concentration and functionalisation. Various research has been conducted with regard to the affect of dose concentration on cell viability.

The two parameters used to monitor this test are concentration of dose and the incubation time. It has been shown using rat erythrocytes (red blood cells) that at MWCNT concentrations of 25mg/mL no adverse effects to the cells were observed.

At concentrations of 50 micro g/mL however erythrocyte haemolysis (breaking of the cell membrane) was increased. One likely explanation is that at these higher concentrations the MWCNTs agglomerate which appear to accelerate

the haemolysis process [8]. Several papers agree that high dose concentrations and prolonged incubation times both increase the induced toxicity and thus decrease cell viability and shows cell viability decreasing significantly in human bronchial epithelial cells.

The trend shows how DNA damage increases considerably with dose concentration of SWCNTs (note: non functionalized SWCNT). The concentration and incubation time of a dose is an

Figure 5: targeting of functionalized CNTs with anti cancer drug to the cancer cells.

area of nanotechnology in cancer treatment which will require much further study, as it will be both important to optimize these for the treatment and eradication of cancerous growths, but will also be important to minimize the body's exposure to the drug (should it prove to have a degree of toxicity). The focus for a large amount of research has been into how the degree of fictionalization affects the CNT toxicity.

This is also likely to be one of the areas of research that receives most attention because active and passive targeting is directly related to the type and degree of fictionalization on the CNT. It has been demonstrated by Kalauger

(2005) that increasing the degree of fictionalization on 6.4 Avenues for Research 12 a SWCNT can dramatically decrease its cytotoxicity. The executive director for the Centre for Biological and Environmental Nanotechnology (CBEN) has said regarding this study. it's the same answer: change the surfaces.

This is an important demonstration that there are general trends in biological responses to nanoparticles. Long side-chain functional groups on SWCNTs can lower toxicity and have been shown to increase the CNTs biocompatibility with cells. This property of CNTs for cancer treatment appears to be particularly promising, as the

functionalisation of CNTs is essential for passive and active cancer treatment [7].

BIOCOMPATIBILITY OF CNTs

An ideal (non-covalent) functionalisation coating should have the following properties (Liu, Tabakman, Welsler and Dai, 2009):

- Coating should be nontoxic and biocompatible
- Coating should be sufficiently stable to resist detachment from nanotubes surface in biological conditions
- Amphiphilic coating molecules should have a low critical micelle concentration so CNT is stable once removed from solution
- Coating should have functional groups which are available for bioconjugation with antibodies or other molecules to create various CNT conjugates for various applications.

IN-VIVO RESEARCH NEWS ABOUT POTENTIAL USE OF CNTs

As the sidewall of SWCNTs is highly hydrophobic, they are practically insoluble in water. Therefore, SWCNTs are functionalized by covalent or noncovalent routes that will help in disentangling the CNT bundles and make them soluble in water. Prepared a solution of SWCNTs wrapped in polyethylene glycol (PEG) with a tumourtargetting cyclic arginine–glycine– aspartic acid peptide to the end of the PEG chains. This solution was injected into mice bearing tumours and it was observed that the targetted SWCNTs accumulated in tumours. Thus potential drug delivery applications have been achieved [9].

With efficient in vivo accumulation of SWCNTs in mice tumours [9]. The above finding has prompted studies to attach a cancer chemotherapy drug doxorubicin (DOX) molecule onto prefunctionalized nanotubes, possibly for *in vivo* cancer therapy. SWCNTs are functionalized noncovalently by a surfactant (phospholipid) (PL)–PEG, ~120 polyethylene oxide (PEO) units) or covalently by PEGylation (~200 PEO units) of COOH-groups on oxidized SWCNTs obtained by treatment with nitric acid. DOX was mixed with

the prefunctionalized SWCNTs and kept overnight at a pH of 9.

The solution was filtered to remove free, unbound DOX and characterized by spectral studies which indicate doxorubicin π -stacking (supramolecular assembly) onto unoccupied surface areas of PEG–SWCNTs forming a forest (PEG)–scrub (DOX) structures on SWCNTs (Figure 1). The DOX-loaded SWCNTs are stable in water and at pH 7.4 physiological buffers.

DOX is a widely used chemotherapy drug and SWCNT without DOX loading did not show any toxic effects on malignant cells. Liu *et al.* have demonstrated that DOXloaded SWCNTs (PL–SWCNT–DOX) induced significant U87 cancer cell death and cell apoptosis similar to free DOX. The main advantage of using SWCNT as a drug carrier compared to free drug is the potential to target delivery for selective destruction of certain types of cells, reducing the toxicity to nontargetted cells. It has also been observed that with decreasing pH, the loading of DOX reduces on SWCNTs.

This is due to increased hydrophilicity and higher solubility of DOX at lower pH caused by increased protonation of –NH₂ groups on DOX. This results in reducing the hydrophobic interaction between DOX and SWCNT, and DOX is released. The pH dependence of binding/release of DOX could be profitably exploited for drug delivery applications.

As the micro-environments of extracellular tissues of tumours and intracellular lysosomes and endosomes are acidic, the situation will potentially facilitate active drug release from SWCNT delivery vehicles. This method provides a novel, easy-to-make formulation of the SWCNT–DOX complex with extremely high drug-loading efficiency, which is remarkably higher than that reported for conventional liposomes and dendrimer drug carriers [9]

And another technique was found by Yale University engineers have found that the defects in carbon nanotubes cause T cell antigens to cluster in the blood and stimulate the body's

natural immune response. Their findings, which appear as the cover article of the April 20 issue of the journal *Langmuir*, could improve current adoptive immunotherapy, a treatment used to boost the body's ability to fight cancer. That is

Carbon Nanotubes Boost Cancer-Fighting Cells

Adoptive immunotherapy involves extracting a patient's blood so that the number of naturally occurring T cells (a type of white blood cell) can reproduce more effectively in the laboratory. Although the body produces its own tumor-fighting T cells, they are often suppressed by the tumor and are too few to be effective. Scientists boost the production of T cells outside the body using different substances that encourage T cell antigens to cluster in high concentrations. The better these substances are at clustering T-cell antigens, the greater the immune cell proliferation. Once enough T cells are produced, the blood is transferred back into the patient's body.

The Yale team had previously reported the unexpected effect that carbon nanotubes had on T cell production. They found that the antigens, when presented on the surface of the nanotubes, stimulated T cell response far more effectively than coating other substrates such as polystyrene in the antigens, even though the total amount of antigens used remained the same. Now they have discovered the reason behind the increased stimulation. They found that the antigens cluster in high concentrations around the tiny defects found in the carbon nanotubes.

"Carbon nanotube bundles resemble a lymph node microenvironment, which has a labyrinth sort of geometry," said Tarek Fahmy, associate professor of chemical engineering and biomedical engineering at Yale and senior author of the paper. The nanotube bundles seem to mimic the physiology and adsorb more antigens, promoting a greater immunological response." Current adoptive immunotherapy takes weeks to produce enough T-cells, but lab tests showed that the nanotubes produced the same T-cell concentration in just one-third the time, Fahmy said.

Carbon nanotubes can cause problems, such as an embolism, when used in the body. But this isn't the case when they are used in blood that has been extracted from the patient, Fahmy said. Next, the team will work on a way to effectively remove the carbon nanotubes from the blood before it is returned to the patient. "We think this is a really interesting use of carbon nanotubes. It's a way to exploit the unique properties of this material for biological application in a safe way."

CONCLUSION

Carbon nanotechnology has proven itself useful in many areas of science, especially in chemical engineering. Innovations in carbon nanotube technology have already revolutionized the world as we know it, and could revolutionize cancer treatments as well if enough time is put into researching the power that they have in killing malignant cells. Researchers and engineers alike are obligated to push to find better cancer fighters and this could be the path that takes them there. If carbon nanotubes are pushed to their full potential, countless lives could be saved from this disease. In the field of CNT technology for cancer treatment, the issues surrounding CNT toxicity remain inconclusive, as there are numerous conflicting studies demonstrating both toxic and non-toxic behaviour. This is in part; it seems, due to the nature of the research being conducted. That is, there is no real benchmark for comparing results.

Due to the range of parameters listed earlier which have been shown to affect CNTs toxicity, this is an area which will require the continual attention of toxicologists in the future. Using just one example, some evidence (Ji et al., 2010) points to Fe (iron) impurities on CNTs at high concentrations increasing the observed cytotoxic response, and other research Azizian et al. (2010) claims the opposite.

Clearly much further study is required in this area before CNT technology can be applied to cancer treatment. That said, it is an extremely promising application of nano-technology and is definitely worth further research, as the current methods for cancer treatments are indiscriminately harmful and only semi-effective.

REFERENCES

1. Singh, R., Pantarotto, D., McCarthy, D., Chaloin, Hoebeke, J., Partidos, C. D., Briand, J.-P.,Prato, M., Bianco, A. and Kostarelos, K. Binding and condensation of plasmid DNA onto functionalized carbon nanotubes: Toward the construction of nanotube-based gene delivery vectors, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2005, 127(12): 4388–4396.
2. Muguruma, H., Matsui, Y. and Shibayama, Y.. Carbon nanotube–plasma polymer-based ampero metric biosensors: Enzyme-friendly platform for ultra sensitive glucose detection, *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics*, 2007, 46(9A): 6078–6082.
3. Tsang, S. C., Chen, Y. K., Harris, P. J. F. and Green, M. L. H. A simple chemical method of opening and filling carbon nanotubes, *Nature*, 1994, 372(6502).
4. Gao, Y, K., DX, C. and CS, O. Spontaneous insertion of dna oligonucleotides into carbon nanotubes, *Nano Letters*, 2003, 3(4).
5. Prato, M., Kostarelos, K. and Bianco, A. Functionalized carbon nanotubes in drug design and discovery. *Accounts of chemical research*, 2008, 41(1): 60–68.
6. Liu, Z., Tabakman, S., Welsher, K. and Dai, H.. Carbon Nanotubes in Biology and Medicine: In vitro and in vivo Detection, Imaging and Drug Delivery., *Nano research*, 2009, 2(2):85–120.
7. Azizian, J., Tahermansouri, H., Biazar, E., Heidari,S. and Khoei, D. C. Functionalization of carboxylated multiwall nanotubes with imidazole derivatives and their toxicity investigations. *International journal of nanomedicine* , 2010, (5): 907–14.
8. Bottini, M., Bruckner, S., Nika, K., Bottini, N.,Bellucci, S., Magrini, A., Bergamaschi, A. and Mustelin, T. Multi-walled carbon nanotubes induce T lymphocyte apoptosis, *Toxicology letters*, 2006, 160(2) :121–6.
9. C. Srinivasan Carbon nanotubes in cancer therapy, *Current science*, 2008, 94(3). 300-301.

2011003026427600